

Analysis of sequence diversity in sub-families of phytochrome-linked effectors

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Abstract

Sequence Similarity Networks allow the integration of protein sequence relationships with complementary data such as functional or spectral information, enabling the visualisation of potential functional connections. Here we describe the use of BLAST-generated E-values or Bit-scores within a network of bacteriophytochrome homologs to emphasize various characteristics of interest and their sequence-level conservation.

Key words

Sequence similarity network, sequence alignment, visualisation, network analysis, bacteriophytochromes, effector families

1. Introduction

According to the sequence-structure-function paradigm, protein function is defined by structure, which is determined by the amino acid sequence [1]. Within individual sub-families of protein classes, identifying conserved features such as the length of structural elements, and

correlating them with other conserved characteristics can be challenging. Sequence Similarity Networks (SSNs) integrate protein sequence relationships with additional orthogonal information, providing deeper understanding of functional connections [2]. Unlike phylogenetic analysis based on distance or parsimony methods, SSNs are not constrained by sample size; in fact, larger datasets enhance the representation of existing sequence relationships. These relationships are determined using NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information) BLAST+ (basic local alignment search tool)-generated E-values or Bit-scores [3]. Duplicate results and self-BLAST entries need to be removed. For small datasets, this can be done manually, for larger ones, a software solution is recommended. To assist with this, we provide analysis scripts available on Github (<https://gitlab.tugraz.at/bioc/ssn>). Curated results are subsequently represented in network form using Cytoscape [4] and yWorks Organic Layout [5], with nodes corresponding to individual proteins and edges representing E-values/Bit-scores. Various characteristics of interest, such as spectral properties, different effector modules or sensor-effector linker length, can be highlighted in the visualised output. Thus, SSNs are a powerful tool for investigating systems like bacteriophytochrome (BphP) effector sub-families, providing insights into and conclusions about the complex signal integration mechanisms involved. This has been successfully used by us in characterising bacteriophytochrome-regulated diguanylate cyclases [6]. Considering the complexity of phytochrome signalling in general [7,8], conservation and correlation of individual characteristics among and across different effector (sub-)families is expected to remain an issue of high interest.

2. Materials

The computational requirements for this bioinformatics method are as follows:

2.1 BLAST+: BLAST+ [3] can be run locally in Windows or Linux. NCBI provides installers and source codes for download (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/doc/blast-help/downloadblastdata.html>) as well as user and help manuals.

2.2 Analysis scripts: Different formats of the analysis scripts are provided, so that each user can choose the most convenient way to run their analysis. Our recommendation is to use the Google Colab notebook format, since it requires no local setup.

In general, the basic requirements are a shell to run commands and the specific programming language interpreter that depends on the chosen method.

The provided script files have been tested with GNU bash 5.1.x, GNU awk 5.3.0, python 3.12.x and pandas 2.2.2

2.3 Cytoscape: Visualisation requires Cytoscape [4] (downloadable from <https://cytoscape.org/download.html>). yFiles [5] for Organic Layout representation are also available for download (<https://www.yworks.com/yfiles-download>).

3. Methods

3.1. Database generation and curation

To generate the SSN data, starting from the unaligned FASTA file (*see Note 1*), an automated script is provided as an online Google Colab notebook (<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1RQssmD8X7ZOGaxOYDUYA5kpxmDIGYmkx>).

After loading the page and giving it the necessary permissions, follow the instructions contained therein.

Alternatively, the analysis can be performed manually with the following steps:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Source	Organism	Order	Class	feature 1	NCBI	UNIPROT	length
2	BphP1	species 1	order 1	Actinobacteria	A	ID_1	ID_A	681
3	BphP2	species 2	order 3	Betaproteobacteria	B	ID_2	ID_B	676
4	BphP3	species 3	order 4	Gammaproteobacteria	D	ID_3	ID_A	689
5	BphP4	species 4	order 4	Gammaproteobacteria	D	ID_4	ID_B	689
6	BphP5	species 5	order 5	Gammaproteobacteria	D	ID_5	ID_A	695
7	BphP6	species 6	order 2	Gammaproteobacteria	C	ID_6	ID_B	683
8	BphP7	species 7	order 3	Betaproteobacteria	B	ID_7	ID_A	659
9	BphP8	species 8	order 2	Gammaproteobacteria	D	ID_8	ID_B	689
10	BphP9	species 9	order 1	Actinobacteria	A	ID_9	ID_A	679

Figure 1: *Information file containing unique ID as well as all relevant features to be visualised in the SSN.*

```
C:\blast-2.16.0+bin>makeblastdb -in FILENAME.fasta -dbtype prot -title TITLE -parse_seqids -out DATABASENAME_db
Building a new DB, current time: 12/13/2024 09:24:06
New DB name: C:\blast-2.16.0+bin\DATABASENAME_db
New DB title: TITLE
Sequence type: Protein
Keep MBits: T
Maximum file size: 3000000000B
Adding sequences from FASTA; added 50 sequences in 0.194746 seconds.
```

Figure 2: *NCBI BLAST+ command line output after database creation. If the database was created successfully, 10 new files should have been added to the corresponding folder.*

3.1.1 (Manual) Database compilation & BLAST

1. Compile a list of unaligned protein sequences in FASTA format (*see Note 2, Note 3*) with unique identifier codes.
2. Create a table containing all required information about the individual entries, such as class/phylum/order, effector module, linker length, spectral properties, ... in CSV format (*see Note 2, Fig. 1*).
3. Build a BLAST database using the command “makeblastdb” in the NCBI BLAST+ environment. The command line input is `makeblastdb -in FILENAME.fasta -dbtype prot -title TITLE -parse_seqids -out DATABASENAME_db`, with FILENAME = name of the FASTA file, TITLE = title of the database, DATABASENAME = name of the created database file (*see Fig.2, Note 4, Note 5*).

Query ID	Subject ID	E-value	Bit-score
BphP1	BphP1	0.0	1339
BphP1	BphP15	0.0	1187
BphP1	BphP9	0.0	1066
BphP1	BphP16	0.0	1022
BphP1	BphP13	0.0	1010
BphP1	BphP13	1.6	23.5
BphP1	BphP10	0.0	915
BphP1	BphP27	5.75e-177	513
BphP1	BphP20	1.67e-164	481
BphP1	BphP25	1.41e-163	478
BphP1	BphP18	2.86e-163	478
BphP1	BphP12	1.97e-162	476
BphP1	BphP21	4.98e-156	460
BphP1	BphP19	9.14e-147	435
BphP1	BphP17	1.17e-92	295
BphP1	BphP22	1.35e-83	271
BphP1	BphP26	3.40e-83	270

Figure 3: *All-vs-all BLAST output file in TSV format containing both E-values and Bit-scores.*

4. Perform an all-vs-all BLAST, where every entry of the database is pairwise BLASTed against every other entry, using the command `blastp -db DATABASENAME_db -query FILENAME.fasta -out OUTPUTNAME.tsv -outfmt "6 qseqid sseqid evaluate bitscore"`, with OUTPUTNAME = name of the TSV output file (see Fig.3, **Note 6**, **Note 7**).

3.1.2 (Manual) BLAST result curation

The Colab notebook can automatically process the TSV file generated by blastb, alternatively:

1. Clone the analysis git repository (<https://gitlab.tugraz.at/D5B8E35025578B91/ssn>).
2. Select the correct script to execute and follow the respective instructions.
3. OUTPUTNAME.tsv is the file generated in the previous steps (3.1.1, see Fig. 4).
4. Following execution of the script, two files will be available: bts.csv and evs.csv (see **Note 6**), already properly formatted.

Figure 4: Colab notebook E-value and Bit-score output files.

Figure 5: Cytoscape file import. Correct assignment of source and target nodes is important.

3.2 SSN visualisation using Cytoscape

1. Import bts.csv or evs.csv under “File” – “Import” – “Network from File”. Under “Advanced Options”, check semicolon as delimiter (*see* Fig. 5, **Note 8**).
2. Import the information CSV file under “File” – “Import” – “Table from File”. Again, choose the correct delimiter (*see* **Note 9**).
3. Under “Layout”, choose “yFiles Organic Layout” from the yFiles family of diagramming software components.

Figure 6: Filter applied to delete *Bit-scores/E-values* corresponding to less sequence identity.

4. Remove edges of higher *E-values*/lower Bit-scores corresponding to less closely related sequence relationships: Choose “Filter” – “Column Filter” choose “evalue”/“bitscore” and create a filter (*see* Fig. 6). The range defined by the numbers corresponds to the selected edges to be deleted. Under “Edit” – “Remove Selected Nodes and Edges”, and proceed with deletion. Re-organise the organic layout to see the effect of the deletions (*see* Fig. 7, **Note 10**, **Note 11**). Proceed until individual nodes or clusters begin to split off.
5. Under “Style”, assign different layout options such as node form, fill colour or border colour for different features to be visualised (*see* Fig. 8, **Note 12**).

Figure 7: *Stepwise deletion of edges representing more distant relationships, here for a Bit-score-based network. Proceed until individual nodes begin to split off entirely. Zoom into the figure for detailed view of the Bit-score deletion process in Cytoscape.*

Figure 8: *Application of style options to highlight various features, represented for example by node colour and shape. Zoom into the figure for detailed view of the style options in Cytoscape using “Discrete Mapping”.*

4. Notes

1. The input FASTA file must be unaligned, with no empty residue spaces.
2. It is suggested to create the information CSV file in parallel to the sequence compilation. Also ensure that all identifier codes are exactly the same in both the FASTA and the CSV file.
3. Some programs or servers tend to cut off identifiers after a set number of characters. This does not appear to be an issue with NCBI BLAST, but keep this in mind when developing naming conventions.
4. If database creation was successful, you can display a list of records in the database using `blastdbcmd -db DATABASENAME_db -entry all -outfmt "OID: %o GI: %g ACC: %a IDENTIFIER: %i"`, or display contents of the database with `blastdbcmd -db DATABASENAME_db -entry all`.

5. If BLAST+ returns “BLAST Database error: Database memory map file error” and there is sufficient computer memory, try installing the BLAST+ executables in a different location than the default selected by the installer.
6. The lower the *E*-value, the more closely two sequences are related. The higher the Bit-score, the higher is sequence similarity. In the choice between these two metrics, Bit-scores are independent of query length. Especially in comparison of photoreceptors with different effector modules, Bit-scores are recommended to correct for differences in sequence length.
7. The output file will be in TSV format and contain the query as well as the subject Seq-ID, in addition to *E*-value/Bit-score.
8. In the import pop-up window, your source and target columns should be recognised as “Source Node – String” (green circle) and “Target Node – String” (red circle with dot), respectively. Bit-scores/*E*-values should be listed as “Edge Attribute – Floating Point”.
9. The first column “ID” in the import window should be the same name as the unique identifier given to your BLASTed sequences (*see Note 2*).
10. Deleted edges cannot necessarily be recovered easily. Make sure to save the network regularly and approach the cut-off-point in a stepwise process.
11. Edge lengths have no meaning: They are adjusted by the organic layout algorithm to create a functional network. All information about degree of sequence relationship is contained in the presence or absence of these edges, depending on the *E*-value/Bit-score cut-off point.
12. For the majority of stylistic representations, choose “Discrete Mapping” and assign individual characteristics defined in the information CSV file (*see Note 2*) different graphical features.

5. References

- [1] Koehler Leman J, Szczerbiak P, Renfrew PD et al (2023) Sequence-structure-function relationships in the microbial protein universe. *Nat. Commun.* 14(1):2351. doi:10.1038/s41467-023-37896-w
- [2] Atkinson HJ, Morris JH, Ferrin TE et al (2009) Using Sequence Similarity Networks for Visualization of Relationships Across Diverse Protein Superfamilies. *PLoS One.* doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0004345
- [3] Altschul SF, Gish W, Miller W et al (1990) Basic local alignment search tool. *JMB.* 215(3):403-10. doi:10.1016/S0022-2836(05)80360-2.
- [4] Shannon P, Markiel A, Ozier O et al (2003) Cytoscape: a software environment for integrated models of biomolecular interaction networks. *Genome Res.* 13(11):2498-504. doi:10.1101/gr.1239303.
- [5] Wiese R, Eiglsperger M, Kaufmann M (2001) yFiles: Visualization and Automatic Layout of Graphs; 2001. *Proceedings of the 9th International Symposium on Graph Drawing (GD 2001)*: Springer-Verlag.
- [6] Böhm C, Gourinchas G, Zweytick S (2022) Characterisation of sequence-structure-function space in sensor-effector integrators of phytochrome-regulated diguanylate cyclases. *Photochem Photobiol Sci.* 21(10):1761-1779. doi:10.1007/s43630-022-00255-7.
- [7] Gourinchas G, Ettl S, Winkler A (2019) Bacteriophytochromes – from informative model systems of phytochrome function to powerful tools in cell biology. *Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.* 57:72-83. doi:10.1016/j.sbi.2019.02.005.

[8] Takala H, Edlund P, Ihalainen J, Westenhoff S (2020) Tips and turns of bacteriophytochrome photoactivation. *Photochem. Photobiol. Sci.* 19(11):1488-1510. doi:10.1039/d0pp00117a.

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